

Kinematic and Muscle Activity Differences in Anterior Cruciate Ligament Injury Risk in Semi-Professional Female Football Players: Influence of Limb Condition and Change of Direction Task

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injuries remain a critical issue in female football, with a prevalence of 0.7 injuries per squad and season. Most injuries occur through non-contact mechanisms, frequently linked to valgus collapse, which emphasizes the importance of quality of movement and motor control strategies. Hamstrings protect against anterior tibial translation during side-cutting, while quadriceps activity increases anterior shear forces, and gastrocnemius contributes to ACL loading by amplifying quadriceps recruitment. Despite this, few prevention studies have incorporated electromyographic (EMG) analysis to identify risk factors. Limb dominance has also been highlighted as an important determinant of injury susceptibility. Therefore, the first objective of this study was to evaluate angular velocity and knee angle kinematics, as well as muscle activity in hamstrings, quadriceps, and gastrocnemius, in players with previous knee injury caused by valgus collapse in the dominant limb (DL), players with previous injury in the non-dominant limb (NDL), and healthy players during three side-cutting tests. **Methods.** A cross-sectional study was conducted with 16 female football players, categorized into Injured Dominant Limb (InjDom), Injured Non-Dominant Limb (InjNDom), and Healthy. Participants performed three change-of-direction tasks (CODAT, GOB, and Turn). Kinematics were assessed using a motion capture system (Qualisys AB, Sweden), while surface EMG (Delsys Europe, UK) measured activity of biceps femoris, semitendinosus, vastus medialis, and gastrocnemius lateralis. Analyses included pre-load and stance phases, considering minimum, peak, and range of motion values, as well as average rectified and peak EMG amplitudes. A two-factor mixed model with pairwise comparisons was applied ($p < 0.05$). **Results.** Injured players displayed altered kinematics and muscle activity compared to Healthy, influenced by limb dominance. InjDom showed greater internal tibial rotation and peak angular velocity in the transverse plane, alongside higher semitendinosus activity during pre-load and increased gastrocnemius activity during stance. **Conclusions.** Differences in kinematic and muscle recruitment outcomes were associated with limb dominance, whereas change of direction amplitude only affected muscle activity during stance. These findings support the inclusion of limb dominance and EMG-based outcomes in ACL injury prevention strategies.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injury rates disproportionately affect females, who are 2-6 times more

likely to suffer from an ACL injury compared to males with 0.7 injuries per squad per season and 0.1 injuries per 1,000 hours of play¹⁻³. ACL injuries impose substantial burdens

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across multiple timeframes: in the short term, due to the prolonged rehabilitation process; in the medium term, because of the elevated risk of reinjury; and in the long term, as a result of kinesiophobia and maladaptive alterations in biomechanical motor patterns⁴⁻⁶. In addition, the ACL injury mechanism most frequently arises from neuromuscular failure during unanticipated, high-intensity actions, typically occurring in reactive defensive roles such as change of direction tasks⁷.

Due to the severity and long-term impact of ACL injuries, current research focuses on identifying ACL risk factors to develop prevention strategies aimed at lowering injury thresholds⁸. As non-contact mechanisms remain the predominant cause of ACL rupture, kinematic and kinetic analyses have primarily aimed to characterize the underlying biomechanical patterns associated with elevated risk. Valgus collapse is recognised by clinical guidelines as main ACL injury mechanism characterized by hip adduction and internal rotation, and knee abduction, incorporating that predispose to medialization of the knee relative to lower limb load line favouring the pivot shift of the femur over tibial plateau that promotes the excessive ligament strains^{9,10}. While most studies link increased internal tibial rotation to a higher risk of ACL injury, recent research suggests that excessive transverse plane movement may be the primary risk factor¹¹⁻¹⁷. This association is supported by research that have identified excessive external rotation as a kinematic parameter implicated in the non-contact ACL injury mechanism, specifically when resulting from femorotibial impingement during dynamic loading conditions¹⁷. Consequently, recent studies advocate for incorporating new outcomes, such as angular velocity, into kinematic analyses, as it reflects the speed of joint movement, closely linked to motor control^{11,12,16}. Therefore, it serves to characterize the direction and quality of control, based on movement velocity during the stabilization task.

Clinical guidelines have established that altered muscle activity promotes ACL injury mechanism developed by proprioceptive failure in neuromuscular control system^{12,18-20}. Indeed, studies such as that of Bencke et al. have applied neurophysiological analysis approaches to investigate the clinical repercussions in the specific subgroup of female football players with ACL injury²¹. Their findings demonstrated a reduction in proprioceptive control mechanisms, which was associated with decreased postural stability and poorer movement quality²¹. Recent literature suggests that the directional nature of the risk associated with neurophysiological patterns of surface electromyographic (EMG) activity varies according to the sequential phase of the functional action, particularly whether it occurs during the pre-loading or loading phase, as in change of direction tasks²¹⁻²³. During the loading phase, female players with a prospective history of ACL injury have been shown to adopt

a compensatory strategy characterized by motor unit hyperactivation, reflected in increased muscle activity, i.e., greater EMG signal amplitude recorded during functional testing¹⁹. In this regard, Jeong et al. Specifically examined muscle activity during the loading phase, demonstrating a significant association between reduced EMG signal amplitude during this phase and improved functional performance in motor task execution¹⁷.

Notably, most of ACL stabilization loading occurs in the sagittal plane, primarily involving the hamstrings, quadriceps, and gastrocnemius muscles^{13,18,24}. Hamstrings play a crucial role as ACL synergist by counteracting anterior tibial translation during sidcutting stabilization manoeuvres^{13,18,19}. Previous research highlights that altered hamstring activity, prior to initial ground contact, is associated with an increased risk of ACL injury^{14,19,25}. Semitendinosus (ST) is particularly significant due to its role as a ‘knee adductor’, contributing to medial joint compartment compression and preventing valgus collapse^{18,19,25}. Valgus collapse is often associated with increased quadriceps activity, which has been suggested to increase anterior shear forces and places excessive strain on the ACL, particularly during the load phase when players re-establish their stability^{13,19,25}. Additionally, recent studies have analysed the role of the gastrocnemius in the stabilization process, identifying its function as ACL antagonist^{24,26}. It may perform a posterior displacement of the femur, thereby contributing to anterior tibial translation and amplifying the anterior shear forces generated by quadriceps contraction during the load phase^{24,26}.

Recent research has introduced limb dominance analysis as a risk factor for increased ACL injury tendency^{4,27,28}. Evidence suggests that football players often exhibit higher thresholds in kinematic and muscle activity outcomes related to ACL injury mechanism in the dominant limb (DL) compared to the non-dominant limb (NDL). This phenomenon is attributed to specific football context that is conditioned by ball interaction and sport-specific competition demands. DL is the often use for kicking the ball for that reason is attributed as ability limb instead of NDL that usually assumes the stabilization role during task. However, the demands of the football environment, shaped by both intrinsic (capability, comfortability, or awareness) and extrinsic (opponent position or game situation) factors, force the player to use the DL for stabilization during high-speed movements as change of direction task^{4,27,28}. Under these conditions, the player does not have sufficient time to decide between using the DL or NDL, leading to the engagement of the DL for a role that it is not usually assigned.

Given the high incidence and considerable burden of ACL injuries, together with persistent sex-related disparities in prevalence, improving functional evaluation strategies in female athletes remains a critical priority. Since non-contact mechanisms, particularly valgus collapse, continue to

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represent the most frequent cause of ACL rupture, examining both the quantity and quality of movement becomes essential. Specifically, analysing knee joint kinematics, angle and angular velocity, alongside neuromuscular parameters, muscle activation patterns, can reveal distinctive biomechanical and motor control differences between players at risk of ACL injury and healthy counterparts, based on acquired biomechanical patterns, thereby clarifying underlying mechanisms of injury susceptibility. In football, functional asymmetry between the DL, primarily responsible for skilled actions, and the NDL, which serves a stabilizing role, further justifies comparative analyses of movement quality and motor control according to limb dominance of the injured limb.

Therefore, the first objective of this study was to evaluate angular velocity and knee angle kinematics of the knee, as well as muscle activity in hamstrings, quadriceps and gastrocnemius, in players with previous knee injury by valgus collapse mechanism in the DL, players with previous knee injury in the NDL and healthy players during three sidcutting tests. The second objective was to evaluate how these biomechanical motor pattern differences were influenced by the amplitude of the angle involved during each type of change of direction task. Therefore, it was hypothesized that players with previous knee injury by valgus collapse mechanism, without surgical treatment, would demonstrate altered kinematic and muscle activity patterns, both between limb dominance conditions of the injured limb and in comparison to healthy players. Additionally, this study suggests that these between-group differences would manifest distinctly across the varying angle involved in each type of change of direction tasks.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study design

This study employed a cross-sectional design and constitutes a sub-analysis derived from a previously published project by Ferrández et al.²⁷ Therefore, the present article focuses on a specific examination of the influence of limb dominance on the acquisition of dysfunctional biomechanical adjustments during functional change-of-direction tasks. Moreover, this sub-analysis refines the sample distribution relative to the original publication, stratifying participants into three groups defined by clinical history and the dominance of the injured limb.

B. Participants

Potential participants were identified from professional female futsal teams (Real Federación de Fútbol de Ceuta). They were eligible if they held an active national futsal license, train for over 8 hours per week, competed in the Second Spanish National Futsal Division, and actively participated in competitions at the time of the study. Participants were allocated to groups based on their clinical history. Injured players were defined as those who had

sustained a previous non-contact knee injury involving valgus collapse without ACL rupture or surgical intervention on their dominant limb (InjDom) or non-dominant limb (InjNDom)^{4,10,20,29}. Limb dominance criteria were determined based on preferred kicking limb²⁸. The control group consisted of players that were injury free and had not previously sustained a knee injury. The Research Ethics Committee of the Community of Aragón approved this study (code PI20/127), which adhered to the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki³⁰. All participants provided written informed consent prior to data collection commencement. For those participating players who were minors, it was also signed by their legal guardian.

C. Procedure

Participants took part in a single testing session and following a warm up, they were required to complete one trial under three different change of direction tasks; (1) Change of Direction and Acceleration Test (CODAT)^{31,32}, (2) Go Back Test (GOB)³³, and (3) Turn test (TURN)^{34,35} (see Figure 1). These tests require performing a change of direction at maximal velocity, but each test involves different amplitudes of directional change. In CODAT and TURN, a 90° change of direction was recorded. However, in CODAT, this occurs after an initial change of direction, followed by two more consecutive. In GOB test, a 180° change of direction was recorded, which includes a coronal braking phase followed by a backward movement. Participants were instructed to change direction on their DL and NDL, depending on their group, to replicate the ACL injury mechanism. The InjDom and Healthy used their DL as the stance limb for each change of direction test, while the InjNDom group used their NDL as the support limb. Prior to data collection, participants completed a familiarization period to avoid learning bias³⁶.

Figure 1. Functional change of direction test: CODAT test, GOB test and TURN test.

The initial point of the test is drawn with a green ball. The green square shows the location of the force plate. Finally, the red cross identifies the change of direction task that was recorded. (A) Change of Direction and Acceleration Test (CODAT), this test combines sprinting mechanics with the stabilization and acceleration required for change of direction movements. It consists of four diagonal change of direction tasks: two at 45° and two at 90°, interspersed with 3-metre sprints and culminating in a 10-metre sprint^{31,32}. (B) Go and Back test (GOB), this test involves a 10 m frontal sprint at maximum possible speed, followed by deceleration and a final backward sprint. It simultaneously incorporates a change of direction and a deceleration task, both of which are common mechanisms associated with ACL injuries³³. (C) TURN test, this test is a modified version of the T-test. It involves a frontal sprint followed by a single pre-planned 90° change of direction, performed once in each direction^{34,35}.

D. Marker and EMG sensor Placement

A total of twenty-six markers were placed on the anterior and posterior superior iliac spines, bilaterally on the greater

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trochanters, medial and lateral femoral epicondyles and medial and lateral malleoli. Non-orthogonal tracking clusters comprising of four markers were positioned on the lateral thighs and lateral shanks. The feet were modelled as single segments with four markers attached to each foot on the calcanei, 1st metatarsal, 5th metatarsal and midfoot. Kinematic data were captured at 250 Hz using a nine-camera 3D motion capture system (Qualisys AB, Göteborg, Sweden)²⁹.

Surface EMG were recorded using four Trigno Avanti (Delsys Inc., USA) wireless sensors sampled at 1000 Hz positioned over the Biceps Femoris (BF), ST, Vastus Medialis (VM) and lateral Gastrocnemius (LG) following the SENIAM guidelines^{19,37}.

E. Data Analysis

Marker trajectories and EMG data were exported to C3D and imported into Visual 3D (C-Motion Inc., Germantown, USA) for analysis. Kinematic data were filtered using a 4th order zero-lag, 8Hz low-pass Butterworth filter³⁴. Knee joint kinematics were calculated from the shank relative to the thigh using an XYZ cardan sequence³⁵. Peak knee kinematics in the sagittal, coronal, and transverse planes were extracted³⁵. The EMG signals were filtered using a second-order Butterworth high-pass filter with a cut off frequency of 40 Hz to minimize movement artifacts and then full wave rectified and low-pass filtered with a 15Hz cut off frequency³⁸. The maximum observed signal from the filtered data across all trials and muscles was used to normalize the average and peak EMG signals during the preparation (PREP) phase, defined as 100ms prior to ground contact to the frame immediately before initial contact and the loading (LOAD) phase defined as initial contact to maximum knee flexion^{13,39}.

F. Sample Size

The sample size was calculated based on a minimum expected difference of 0.16 (SD 0.11) in BF muscle activity during PREP phase in a sidcutting maneuver³⁹ using the GRANMO 8.0 calculator, considering an alpha risk of 0.05, a beta risk of 0.20, and a two-sided test. A target sample of 16 participants, eight per group, was required.

G. Statistical Analysis

Mean and standard deviation of the DL in InjDom and NDL in InjNDom of the injured participants and DL of the Healthy participants were computed, as no significant differences were observed between DL and NDL in the Healthy participants. The data were evaluated for the normality of the distribution scores using the Shapiro-Wilk test.

Two factor Mixed Model (3x3) ANOVA tests were used to explore kinematic differences between (InjDom, InjNDom and Healthy) during the three different movement tasks, and

separate tests were conducted for the PREP and LOAD phases for muscle activity. For significant main effects, pairwise comparisons were conducted to explore differences between limbs and tasks. For significant interactions, separate one way ANOVA test for each task were conducted. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$ and all statistical analysis were performed using SPSS software v.25 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

III. RESULTS

Five participants were allocated to the InjDom group, 3 to the InjNDom group and 8 to the healthy group, based on their clinical history. The average age was 23.4 ± 5.03 years with an average height of 1.62 ± 0.06 m. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics, main effects and interactions for sagittal, coronal and transverse plane knee kinematics. In the sagittal plane, Mixed Model ANOVA tests revealed a significant main effect of limb for minimum knee flexion angular velocity ($p = 0.016$) and knee flexion-extension angular velocity range of motion ($p = 0.043$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons for minimum flexion angular velocity showed the InjDom demonstrated significantly greater flexion angular velocity compared to InjNDom ($p=0.005$) and a trend towards significance ($p=0.053$) for InjDom showing higher angular velocity compared to Healthy. For knee flexion-extension angular velocity range of motion, pairwise comparisons showed significantly greater angular velocity range in the InjDom compared to InjNDom ($p=0.014$) and the Healthy demonstrated significantly greater angular velocity range of motion compared to InjNDom ($p=0.041$) (Table 4). In the coronal plane, Mixed Model ANOVA tests showed a significant main effect of limb on minimum knee abduction angular velocity ($p = 0.039$) with post-hoc pairwise comparisons showing significantly greater abduction angular velocity in the InjDom compared to InjNDom ($p=0.017$), and a trend towards significance ($p=0.055$) with the InjDom showing a higher abduction angular velocity compared to the Healthy (Table 4).

In the transverse plane, Mixed Model ANOVA tests showed a significant main effect of limb on knee internal-external rotation range of motion ($p = 0.008$) and peak knee internal rotation angular velocity ($p = 0.021$). For peak internal rotation angular velocity, post-hoc pairwise comparison showed significantly greater internal angular velocity InjDom compared to InjNDom ($p=0.038$), and InjDom to the Healthy ($p=0.008$). For internal-external knee range of motion, post-hoc pairwise comparisons showed significantly higher knee range of motion in the InjDom compared to the Healthy ($p=0.002$) (Table 4).

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Table I. Mean (SDs) and results of the main and interaction effects from the two-factor mixed linear model for peak sagittal, coronal and transverse plane knee kinematics during the CODAT, GOB and Turn tasks.

Variables	CODAT			GOB			TURN			Task p value	Limb p value	Interaction effect
	Injured Dom	Injured Non-Dom	Healthy	Injured Dom	Injured Non Dom	Healthy	Injured Dom	Injured Non Dom	Healthy			
Sagittal Plane												
<i>Joint Angle (°)</i>												
Minimum Knee Flexion Angle	19.73 ±4.42	17.93 ±5.31	23.64 ±8.77	21.79 ±4.98	17.28 ±1.33	21.22 ±11.96	22.52 ±1.79	22.87 ±3.35	23.83 ±9.11	0.523	0.506	0.921
Peak Knee Flexion Angle	55.65 ±8.67	50.30 ±8.57	54.30 ±12.04	63.68 ±10.51	59.89 ±11.34	59.46 ±8.18	64.22 ±11.80	53.00 ±1.95	58.41 ±14.88	0.158	0.330	0.954
Knee Flexion-Extension Angle ROM	35.92 ±10.78	32.37 ±6.50	30.66 ±11.17	41.89 ±10.54	42.61 ±11.43	38.23 ±10.91	41.70 ±12.92	30.13 ±3.02	34.59 ±12.13	0.162	0.322	0.878
<i>Angular Velocity (°/s)</i>												
Minimum Knee Flexion Angular Velocity	-589.02 ±91.12	-397.76 ±75.56	-501.68 ±126.55	-480.53 ±65.49	-432.53 ±60.00	-471.95 ±104.43	-591.51 ±94.57	-445.93 ±64.33	-485.78 ±124.02	0.438	0.016*	0.584
Peak Knee Flexion-Extension Angular Velocity	78.31 ±176.79	-11.16 ±15.18	142.30 ±225.42	11.88 ±67.08	4.75 ±17.91	52.60 ±83.34	-8.65 ±11.21	8.25 ±22.50	-21.42 ±29.10	0.157	0.452	0.356
Knee Flexion-Extension Angular Velocity ROM	667.33 ±177.78	386.61 ±74.38	643.98 ±197.75	492.42 ±89.02	437.28 ±49.48	524.55 ±163.86	582.86 ±100.18	454.17 ±84.53	464.36 ±119.65	0.394	0.043*	0.309
Frontal Plane												
<i>Joint Angle (°)</i>												
Minimum Knee Abduction Angle	-8.50 ±5.52	-3.63 ±5.11	-7.87 ±4.24	-5.32 ±5.63	-2.91 ±5.65	-8.80 ±6.96	-8.09 ±6.79	-5.36 ±4.33	-6.65 ±4.99	0.880	0.222	0.816
Peak Knee Abduction/Adduction Angle	-0.30 ±3.25	2.90 ±3.09	-2.26 ±3.99	2.74 ±6.75	2.57 ±4.84	2.91 ±7.56	0.42 ±4.47	1.07 ±1.84	1.76 ±6.80	0.464	0.813	0.663
Knee Abduction-Adduction Angle ROM	8.20 ±3.84	6.53 ±5.89	5.61 ±2.52	8.07 ±3.11	5.48 ±1.15	11.71 ±5.50	8.51 ±3.11	6.43 ±2.54	8.41 ±3.87	0.558	0.275	0.284
<i>Angular Velocity (°/s)</i>												
Minimum Knee Abduction Angular Velocity	-152.07 ±64.94	-61.23 ±65.29	-114.89 ±37.91	-155.34 ±94.49	-109.84 ±35.65	-133.43 ±45.78	-194.07 ±152.06	-89.85 ±96.63	-105.27 ±51.92	0.543	0.039*	0.832
Peak Knee Adduction Angular Velocity	188.61 ±74.90	208.58 ±86.54	140.87 ±98.08	202.80 ±89.94	151.65 ±22.20	175.43 ±85.87	256.25 ±126.33	225.11 ±15.35	179.37 ±91.62	0.402	0.230	0.794
Knee Abduction-Adduction Angular Velocity ROM	340.68 ±122.26	269.81 ±138.06	255.76 ±127.85	358.14 ±183.18	261.49 ±37.63	308.86 ±92.26	450.32 ±270.31	314.96 ±108.28	284.64 ±108.42	0.585	0.096	0.893
Transverse Plane												
<i>Joint Angle (°)</i>												
Minimum Knee External Rotation Angle	-0.12 ±8.83	-3.95 ±8.96	-0.97 ±8.48	-7.14 ±10.44	-6.48 ±11.05	-4.18 ±9.51	-9.10 ±9.77	-1.25 ±6.99	-2.44 ±7.35	0.487	0.616	0.711
Peak Knee Internal Rotation Angle	12.13 ±8.30	10.60 ±9.04	8.19 ±7.33	7.23 ±6.73	5.38 ±7.80	7.92 ±8.63	11.51 ±7.19	10.56 ±5.62	6.19 ±5.76	0.497	0.506	0.803
Knee Internal-External Rotation Angle ROM	12.24 ±6.22	14.55 ±3.57	9.16 ±4.40	14.37 ±5.77	11.86 ±4.27	12.10 ±5.54	20.61 ±6.56	11.81 ±5.58	8.63 ±5.14	0.708	0.008*	0.136
<i>Angular Velocity (°/s)</i>												
Minimum Knee External Rotation Angular Velocity	-83.32 ±111.11	-118.76 ±61.60	-164.32 ±145.82	-190.59 ±147.05	-146.07 ±73.27	-254.06 ±134.48	-118.65 ±66.32	-93.64 ±51.18	-176.01 ±96.89	0.236	0.111	0.977
Peak Knee Internal Rotation Angular Velocity	250.85 ±203.84	257.01 ±31.86	215.68 ±126.86	304.29 ±141.01	213.23 ±79.95	233.24 ±115.39	467.87 ±178.97	197.76 ±89.93	215.80 ±88.08	0.530	0.021*	0.208
Knee Internal-External Rotation Angular Velocity ROM	334.17 ±293.31	375.78 ±65.30	380.00 ±249.73	494.89 ±121.78	359.30 ±27.79	487.30 ±221.62	586.52 ±160.34	291.40 ±126.56	391.81 ±141.91	0.598	0.298	0.398

*Denotes significance

(Injured Dom) Injured players in dominant limb | (Injured Non-Dom) Injured players in non-dominant limb

Figure 2. Sagittal Plane for InjDom, InjNDom and Healthy players angular velocity in the CODAT Test during the load Phase

Figure 3. Coronal Plane for InjDom, InjNDom and Healthy players angular velocity in the CODAT Test during the load Phase

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Figure 4. Coronal Plane for InjDom, InjNDom and Healthy players angular velocity in the CODAT Test during the load Phase

Table 2 and 3 show the descriptive statistics and Mixed Model ANOVA tests for average and peak muscle activity for the PREP and LOAD phases, respectively. During the PREP phase, significant main effect was seen for limb for average ST muscle activity ($p = 0.033$) (Table 2). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons showed significant greater average ST muscle activity in InjDom compared to InjNDom ($p=0.048$), and significantly greater average ST muscle activity in InjDom compared to Healthy group ($p=0.014$) (Table 4). In the LOAD phase, Mixed Model ANOVA tests showed a significant interaction between task and limb for peak LG muscle activity ($p = 0.040$) (Table 3). Post-hoc one-way ANOVAs revealed that for TURN, peak LG muscle activity was significantly higher for InjDom compared to Healthy ($p = 0.009$) (Table 5). There were no differences between limbs for either the GOB or CODAT ($p>0.05$) (Table 5).

Table II. Mean (SDs) and results of the main and interaction effects from the two-factor mixed linear model for peak muscle activity for Biceps Femoris, Semitendinosus, Vastus Medialis and Lateral Gastrocnemius during the CODAT, GOB and Turn tasks during preparation phase.

Variables	CODAT			GOB			TURN			Task p value	Limb p value	Interaction effect
	Injured Dom	Injured Non-Dom	Healthy	Injured Dom	Injured Non Dom	Healthy	Injured Dom	Injured Non Dom	Healthy			
Average Biceps Femoris	0.17±0.06	0.08±0.02	0.13±0.11	0.13±0.04	0.11±0.03	0.10±0.07	0.18±0.04	0.10±0.03	0.14±0.12	0.550	0.132	0.893
Peak Biceps Femoris	0.69±0.29	0.52±0.08	0.59±0.37	0.54±0.19	0.47±0.15	0.38±0.25	0.77±0.21	0.53±0.30	0.53±0.42	0.249	0.207	0.944
Average Semitendinosus	0.22±0.05	0.09±0.07	0.15±0.07	0.18±0.05	0.20±0.06	0.16±0.06	0.20±0.07	0.16±0.09	0.14±0.07	0.435	0.033*	0.192
Peak Semitendinosus	0.86±0.21	0.46±0.39	0.75±0.23	0.63±0.20	0.77±0.20	0.63±0.22	0.72±0.27	0.90±0.18	0.63±0.18	0.645	0.651	0.132
Average Vastus Medialis	0.11±0.05	0.11±0.08	0.08±0.05	0.07±0.04	0.09±0.02	0.07±0.04	0.10±0.04	0.09±0.04	0.07±0.05	0.386	0.260	0.960
Peak Vastus Medialis	0.52±0.22	0.45±0.10	0.43±0.31	0.42±0.22	0.54±0.20	0.33±0.18	0.56±0.28	0.47±0.15	0.46±0.25	0.711	0.444	0.843
Average Lateral Gastrocnemius	0.08±0.04	0.07±0.02	0.08±0.06	0.05±0.03	0.06±0.05	0.07±0.04	0.05±0.02	0.05±0.03	0.05±0.04	0.305	0.887	0.994
Peak Lateral Gastrocnemius	0.40±0.22	0.41±0.11	0.50±0.33	0.25±0.16	0.27±0.26	0.36±0.24	0.45±0.28	0.25±0.15	0.32±0.30	0.343	0.731	0.792

*Denotes significance

(Injured Dom) Injured players in dominant limb | (Injured Non-Dom) Injured players in non-dominant limb

Table III. Mean (SDs) and results of the main and interaction effects from the two-factor mixed linear model for peak muscle activity for Biceps Femoris, Semitendinosus, Vastus Medialis and Lateral Gastrocnemius during the CODAT, GOB and Turn tasks during load phase.

Variables	CODAT			GOB			TURN			Task p value	Limb p value	Interaction effect
	Injured Dom	Injured Non-Dom	Healthy	Injured Dom	Injured Non Dom	Healthy	Injured Dom	Injured Non Dom	Healthy			
Average Biceps Femoris	0.20±0.03	0.10±0.05	0.13±0.09	0.10±0.03	0.11±0.03	0.08±0.07	0.15±0.04	0.14±0.04	0.13±0.08	0.092	0.210	0.456
Peak Biceps Femoris	0.89±0.16	0.59±0.31	0.69±0.31	0.48±0.20	0.76±0.27	0.47±0.40	0.63±0.25	0.84±0.28	0.67±0.34	0.397	0.581	0.363
Average Semitendinosus	0.14±0.07	0.07±0.06	0.14±0.07	0.10±0.02	0.09±0.02	0.10±0.05	0.15±0.09	0.10±0.03	0.11±0.05	0.420	0.199	0.763
Peak Semitendinosus	0.68±0.31	0.58±0.48	0.74±0.24	0.52±0.11	0.53±0.17	0.63±0.28	0.54±0.29	0.67±0.28	0.73±0.26	0.489	0.355	0.950
Average Vastus Medialis	0.20±0.06	0.19±0.03	0.12±0.04	0.13±0.05	0.14±0.04	0.10±0.07	0.14±0.06	0.21±0.02	0.16±0.09	0.059	0.067	0.281
Peak Vastus Medialis	0.99±0.01	0.78±0.15	0.73±0.31	0.64±0.27	0.74±0.25	0.49±0.32	0.63±0.23	0.85±0.17	0.81±0.32	0.136	0.499	0.235
Average Lateral Gastrocnemius	0.15±0.08	0.15±0.06	0.14±0.07	0.12±0.08	0.11±0.07	0.08±0.04	0.16±0.07	0.15±0.11	0.08±0.04	0.283	0.124	0.798
Peak Lateral Gastrocnemius	0.64±0.33	0.78±0.19	0.88±0.24	0.50±0.33	0.55±0.34	0.61±0.35	0.89±0.15	0.62±0.34	0.47±0.25	0.204	0.968	0.040*

*Denotes significance

(Injured Dom) Injured players in dominant limb | (Injured Non-Dom) Injured players in non-dominant limb

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Table IV. Knee kinematic and EMG pairwise comparisons for significant limb and task main effects

Variable – Knee kinematic		Mean Difference	p value	95% Confidence Intervals for Differences	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
<i>Sagittal Plane</i>					
Minimum Knee Flexion Angular Velocity	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	-128.28	0.005*	-215.73	-40.83
	Injured Dom and Healthy	-67.22	0.053	-135.48	1.05
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	61.07	0.136	-20.00	142.14
Knee Flexion-Extension Angular Velocity ROM	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	154.85	0.014*	32.78	276.92
	Injured Dom and Healthy	36.57	0.441	-58.72	131.86
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	-118.28	0.041*	-231.44	-5.11
<i>Frontal Plane</i>					
Minimum Knee Abduction Angular Velocity	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	-80.19	0.017*	-144.67	-15.71
	Injured Dom and Healthy	-49.30	0.055	-99.63	1.03
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	30.89	0.300	-28.89	90.66
<i>Transverse Plane</i>					
Peak Knee Internal Rotation Angular Velocity	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	118.34	0.038*	6.85	229.83
	Injured Dom and Healthy	119.43	0.008*	32.40	206.46
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	1.09	0.983	-102.27	104.45
Knee Internal-External Rotation Joint Angle ROM	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	3.00	0.192	-1.57	7.57
	Injured Dom and Healthy	5.78	0.002*	2.21	9.35
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	2.78	0.193	-1.46	7.02
Variable – EMG					
Average Semitendinosus Preparation Phase	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	0.054	0.048*	0.00	0.11
	Injured Dom and Healthy	0.053	0.014*	0.01	0.10
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	-0.25	0.978	-0.05	0.05

*Denotes significance

(Injured Dom) Injured players in dominant limb | (Injured Non-Dom) Injured players in non-dominant limb

Table V. Pairwise comparison for limb condition in each task for Lateral Gastrocnemius peak load phase variable.

Variable		Mean Difference	p value	95% Confidence Intervals for Differences	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
<i>Peak Lateral Gastrocnemius load phase</i>					
CODAT	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	-0.14	0.482	-0.56	0.28
	Injured Dom and Healthy	-0.24	0.136	-0.57	0.09
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	-0.10	0.587	-0.49	0.29
GOB	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	-0.05	0.833	-0.49	0.60
	Injured Dom and Healthy	-0.12	0.563	-0.54	0.31
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	-0.06	0.793	-0.57	0.44
TURN	Injured Dom and Injured Non-Dom	0.27	0.152	-0.65	0.11
	Injured Dom and Healthy	0.42	0.009*	0.12	0.72
	Injured Non-Dom and Healthy	0.15	0.370	-0.20	0.51

*Denotes significance

(Injured Dom) Injured players in dominant limb | (Injured Non-Dom) Injured players in non-dominant limb

IV. DISCUSSION

This study investigated the differences in kinematic and muscle activity outcomes associated with ACL injury mechanisms influenced by limb dominance condition during functional change of direction tasks. Therefore, it compared players with previous knee injuries by valgus collapse mechanism in DL or NDL and healthy players. Additionally, it examined whether these differences were influenced by the amplitude and direction of the change of direction task. The results support the hypothesis that players with previous knee injury, based on clinical history, exhibit different functional motor pattern compared to healthy players. And it was influenced by limb dominance, with significant differences observed among InjDom, InjNDom, and Healthy players in both kinematic and muscle activity patterns. However, no significant differences were found between the three functional tasks evaluated, in either kinematic or muscle activity patterns. Therefore, no differences were observed in the motor pattern based on the amplitude or direction of the angle involved in each change of direction task. Kinematic differences between InjDom and InjNDom were observed across all planes, while in Healthy, differences

emerged only in the transverse plane relative to InjDom. InjDom players demonstrated greater angular velocities in all planes. This suggests that most kinematic differences are better reflected in angular velocity rather than peak joint angles, which only reached significance between the InjDom and Healthy in the transverse plane. These findings align with recent studies that emphasize angular velocity as a crucial factor in assessing kinematic variability^{11,12,40,41}. Specifically, Aoki et al. observed valgus collapse without accounting for angular velocity variations, limiting the detection of dynamic knee movements across multiple planes, critical for assessing injury risk.¹² While InjDom and InjNDom exhibited similar knee angles during the LOAD phase, InjDom reached these angles at significantly higher angular velocities. Butler et al. reported a positive correlation between higher angular velocities and increased knee abduction moment, a key risk factor for ACL injury¹⁶. Notably, this correlation was observed only in the injured limb for ACL injured players. This may reflect a less controlled motor pattern in InjDom, resulting in faster movements^{39,40}. In contrast, InjNDom have similar angular velocities to Healthy, suggesting more controlled motor patterns with less reliance on rapid

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adjustments. Consequently, InjDom might be more likely to exhibit significantly higher-risk kinematic profiles across all planes of motion compared to InjNDom.

In the sagittal plane, kinematics revealed that InjDom exhibited significantly higher flexion-extension range of motion and flexion angular velocity. As illustrated in Figure 2, most of these differences are concentrated within the first 25% of the LOAD phase. During this interval, InjDom exhibits more pronounced slope in the negative or flexion direction compared to InjNDom and Healthy. These findings suggest that the highly kinematic variability this plane occurs in the initial LOAD phase. InjDom displaying faster and less controlled motor patterns in flexion direction, which suggest an increase in knee stabilization demands^{12,24,39,40}. This reduced control in sagittal plane may contribute to increased ACL loading, as emphasized by Nasser et al., who identified the main peak in ACL force occurring at approximately 14% of the LOAD phase, with over 94% of the ACL force generated in the sagittal plane^{12,20,24}. In addition, the angular velocity difference observed in the initial LOAD phase is likely connected to altered muscular activity during the PREP phase. Since the limb is non-weightbearing before the LOAD phase, its kinematics are solely influenced by muscle activity. This highlights the importance of integrating mixed kinematic and muscle activity analysis to better understand the underlying motor control patterns throughout the entire maneuver¹⁷.

Muscle activity analysis reveals that during the PREP phase, InjDom and Healthy exhibit significantly higher average rectified ST muscle activity compared to InjNDom, with increases of 54% and 53%, respectively. According to Zebis et al., the ST plays a crucial role in knee stability countering valgus forces^{18,25}. Recent findings suggest that players with lower neuromuscular adaptability show increased muscle activity to stabilize sudden imbalances^{20,42}. In our study, InjDom players demonstrate higher ST muscle activity throughout the PREP phase, potentially linked to the higher angular velocity observed in these players during the early LOAD phase across all planes of motion. This may result from the alignment of the angular velocity direction with the primary antagonist functions of the ST^{18,43}. Consequently, the increased ST muscle activity in InjDom during the PREP phase, could impair motor control leading to delayed activation during the LOAD phase^{19,20,41}. This delay may explain the higher angular velocity observed in extension, in valgus and in internal rotation mechanisms closely associated with ACL injury risk as described in the literature^{10,11}. In summary, InjDom exhibit reduced motor control due to excessive ST actEMG during PREP phase, contributing to biomechanical imbalances during the LOAD phase, which may be linked to ACL injury mechanisms. In the coronal plane, Figure 3, InjDom initiated the LOAD phase with the highest speeds in the negative or valgus direction. These

findings are consistent with research identifying valgus collapse as a key ACL injury risk factor⁴⁴. Similarly, in the transverse plane, Figure 4, InjDom exhibited the greatest internal tibial rotation direction in the initial LOAD phase. This is aligned with Hewett et al. who described the axial forces increasing compression on the lateral side of the knee during valgus collapse⁴⁵. This compression, along with the posterior slope of the lateral tibial plateau, increases internal tibial rotation, as demonstrated by Kikuchi et al., who found a significant correlation between tibial slope compression and internal rotation¹⁴. The significant differences reached in the coronal and transverse planes highlights the importance of multiplanar approach in assessing motor patterns during a functional task. These findings align with research linking higher angular velocities, especially in these planes, to increased knee abduction moments, a key ACL injury mechanism⁴⁶. Finally, in the transverse plane, InjDom showed more internal-external tibial rotation range of motion and peak internal rotation angular velocity compared to Healthy. Figure 4 illustrated greater oscillation in InjDom during LOAD phase, while Healthy remains more stable since initial contact. This may reflect reduced motor control in InjDom, accompanied by an increased range of motion in this plane. These are consistent with research indicating that greater transverse plane motion is associated with elevated ACL injury risk^{11,45}.

Muscle activity during the LOAD phase shows that InjDom demonstrated 42% higher peak LG muscle activity than Healthy, observed exclusively in the TURN test. However, due to its anatomical position, the gastrocnemius enables posterior femoral translation and posterior knee compression^{12,17,24}. This interaction synergizes with the quadriceps to generate anterior tibial shear forces, increasing ACL load^{12,17,24}. As described by Nasser et al., this interaction reaches its peak early in the LOAD phase, along with the previously mentioned kinematic imbalances¹². Therefore, the increased LG peak envelope observed in InjDom may indicate an elevated risk of ACL injury. According to Picot et al., this could be attributed to muscle compensation related to dysfunctional hamstrings muscle activity in InjDom¹⁹. This pattern may raise immediate ACL injury risk and contribute to long-term vulnerability^{4,12,19}.

The only significance observed between InjNDom and Healthy indicates that InjNDom exhibited a lower flexion-extension range of motion angular velocity, suggesting better motor control. As explained in recent research, this could be attributed to the reduced stabilization functionality of DL, analyzed limb in Healthy, conditioned by futsal specific environment^{4,21}. The DL is used for ball interaction, so is less trained for stabilization compared to the NDL^{21,22}. Consequently, increased angular velocity may reflect rapid compensatory adjustments resulting from reduced stabilization capacity^{4,21,23,47}. This finding may support that

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limb dominance influences stabilization strategies based on the specific sport-related role of the injured limb²³.

V. LIMITATIONS

A limitation of this study is its exclusive focus on knee kinematics, as knee motion is influenced by the kinematics of the entire lower limb. Including motion data from the hip and ankle could offer a more comprehensive understanding of knee motion patterns and reveal functional differences between players at risk of ACL injury. Furthermore, incorporating gluteal muscle analysis would be valuable, as these muscles play a key role in controlling hip movement, which in turn affects knee stability, particularly in the transverse plane.

VI. CLINICAL CONTRIBUTIONS

This study highlights the growing trend of incorporating muscle activity analysis, as neuromuscular factor, into ACL injury risk identification studies. In synergy with kinematic variables such as angular velocity may provide more sensitive information to identify players at risk of ACL injury. Lastly, since the study was conducted with active players who had previously suffered an injury due to valgus collapse, we may suppose that in part, the described risk patterns may be a result of dysfunctional compensation. Therefore, these risky motor control patterns should be used to design more effective injury prevention programs aimed at targeting these movement strategies.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This study identified differences in kinematics, in particular knee angular velocity, and muscle activity between players at risk of ACL injury and healthy players. These differences were influenced by limb dominance condition in kinematic and muscle activity outcomes, however the amplitude and direction of the change of direction did not influence kinematics or muscle activity strategies.

This highlights the importance of assessing kinematics alongside specific muscle activity during functional tests, replicating ACL injury mechanisms, to better determine player risk profiles and design more effective.

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